

FAIR PUBLISHING SELF-ASSESSMENT GRID
Template

Dataset name

Dataset summary

Data sources

Data expressions

Comments

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Findability

FAIR principle F1

(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

FAIR principle F2

Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>

FAIR principle F3

Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>

FAIR principle F4

(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>

FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Accessibility

FAIR principle A1

[\(Meta\)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol](#)

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

FAIR principle A1.1

The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

FAIR principle A1.2

The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

FAIR principle A2

Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

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FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Interoperability

FAIR principle II

(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>

FAIR principle I2

(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

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FAIR principle I3

(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

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FAIR PRINCIPLES REVIEW

Reusability

FAIR principle R1

(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

<i>FAIR implementations</i>	<i>FAIR enablers</i>	<i>FAIR challenges</i>

FAIR principle R1.1

(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

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FAIR principle R1.2

(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

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FAIR principle R1.3

(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

FAIR implementations

FAIR enablers

FAIR challenges

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